

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

INTRODUCTION

Welcome to the 2022 edition of SPARC Europe's Survey of European academic libraries regarding Open Education (OE) and Open Education Resources (OER).

We define OE as resources, tools and practices that are free of legal, financial and technical barriers and can be fully used, shared and adapted in the digital environment.

We define OER as learning, teaching and research materials that reside in the public domain or are under copyright that have been released under an open license, that permit no-cost access, re-use, re-purpose, adaptation and redistribution by others.

This survey was developed in consultation with members of the European Network of Open Education Librarians (ENOEL): The aim of this survey is to explore the work done by academic librarians to implement the UNESCO OER Recommendation, published in Nov 2019, and is structured around its five areas of action.

We plan to use the collected data to organise our activities going forward to provide you with Open Education support in the future.

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

SURVEY OVERVIEW

Taking the survey

Please submit only one response per organisation. We ask that this be completed by the individual most responsible for OE. This may be an OE Librarian, a Teaching & Learning Librarian, or perhaps the Library Director.

Only questions marked with an asterisk * are mandatory.

You don't need to complete the survey in one sitting - you can close it and return later. Leaving the survey via the exit button on the top right of the page saves your progress. You can then return to the survey at the same point, using the same link and the device you started on.

Your institution may not be active on the full range of issues we ask about. Please do not be discouraged: all answers will help us understand the current status of OE in academic libraries in Europe.

The survey takes approximately 15 minutes to complete. A PDF is downloadable [here](#).

For questions, please reach out to survey@sparceurope.org.

Ethics and data protection policy

The survey is managed by SPARC Europe. Answers will be reported in aggregate in a report, personal data will be removed before the dataset is deposited on Zenodo with a CC0 licence. For more on our ethics and data protection policy, see [here](#).

You may supply your name and contact details to be informed of the outcomes of this study and to answer any follow-up questions. No personal information is required to submit a response.

We will share the results in late 2022 on the ENOEL webpage.

Begin survey

By clicking 'Next' you confirm that you understand and agree to complete the survey.

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

ABOUT YOU AND YOUR ORGANISATION

* 1. Which of the following best describes your organisation?

- University / Comprehensive institution (e.g. covering all or most academic disciplines)
- University of Applied Sciences (college-type or professional education institution which does not award PhDs, or does so in only a few disciplines)
- Technical university / University of technology
- Distance learning university
- Specialised institution (e.g. medical science, music and arts school)
- Teaching college
- Other (please specify)

* 2. In what country is your organisation based?

* 3. What is the name of your organisation?

* 4. Are you a decision-maker in your library/institution or are you in a more supportive role?

- Decision maker
- In a supportive role
- Other (please specify)

5. How long have you been involved in OE?

- less than 1 year
- 1-5 years
- 6-10 years
- more than 10 years
- I am not involved in OE

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

YOUR DETAILS

* 6. We would like to contact you with the results of this survey and to inform you of future Open Education activities and surveys. Do you consent to being contacted by SPARC Europe for these purposes?

Your answer to this question has no impact on your survey response.

Yes

No

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

YOUR DETAILS (continued)

7. Your details

Name

Email Address

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN OPEN EDUCATION

* 8. How familiar are you with the UNESCO OER Recommendation and its areas of actions?

- Extremely familiar
- Very familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Not so familiar
- Not at all familiar

9. What actions are you taking to implement the UNESCO OER Recommendation?

- We are implementing the Recommendation
- We have adapted or reviewed our strategy accordingly
- We are discussing options
- We have taken no actions to date
- Don't know

10. To what extent did the COVID-19 pandemic affect OE at your institution?

- A great deal
- A lot
- A moderate amount
- A little
- None at all
- Don't know

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

BUILDING CAPACITY

This section focuses on understanding the role and capacity of your library in relation to OE/OER.

* 11. What role does your library take in advancing OE or OER in your organisation?

- A lead role
- A support role
- We are still deciding
- We do not have a role
- Don't know

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

BUILDING CAPACITY (continued)

12. Which library department, if any, takes the lead in any areas of Open Education / OER efforts?

- Collection management
- Innovation
- Open Education department
- Scholarly communications
- Senior management
- Student services
- Teaching and learning support
- Research support
- Other (please specify)

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

BUILDING CAPACITY (continued)

13. Does your organisation have a formal task force, committee or other entity with an Open Education focus?

Please choose one response per row.

	Yes	No	Don't know
At an institution-wide level	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
At a library level	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please specify if "Other"

14. Please briefly tell us how you work together on OE/OER with other departments within the library or outside of it

15. What has been your most important tool, medium or event to promote and communicate change in favour of OE and/or OER?

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

BUILDING CAPACITY (continued)

16. What services do you provide that relate to Open Education?

Please choose as many that apply

- Advice on copyright and open licensing
- Collection management / dealing with education publishers and aggregators
- Course pack provision
- Creation of open textbooks
- Data curation & interoperability
- Discovery services
- Information literacy, including open education
- Knowledge exchange
- OER co-creation (e.g. toolkits, libguides or others with CC licenses)
- OER provision (evaluation, selection, etc) to complement courses
- Management & storage service (e.g. repositories)
- Metadata to index digital resources
- Participatory design
- Training / Education
- Other (please specify)

- None of the above

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

BUILDING CAPACITY (continued)

17. To what extent does your library have the skills it needs to support OE in these areas?

Please select one option per row

	Full set of skills	Many skills	Limited skills	No skills	Don't know
Advice on copyright and open licensing	<input type="radio"/>				
Collection management / dealing with education publishers and aggregators	<input type="radio"/>				
Course pack provision	<input type="radio"/>				
Creation of open textbooks	<input type="radio"/>				
Data curation & interoperability	<input type="radio"/>				
Discovery services	<input type="radio"/>				
Information literacy, including open education	<input type="radio"/>				
Knowledge exchange	<input type="radio"/>				
OER co-creation (e.g. toolkits, libguides or others with CC licenses)	<input type="radio"/>				
OER provision (evaluation, selection, etc) to complement courses	<input type="radio"/>				
Management & storage service (e.g. repositories)	<input type="radio"/>				
Metadata to index digital resources	<input type="radio"/>				
Participatory design	<input type="radio"/>				
Training / Education	<input type="radio"/>				
[Insert text from Other]	<input type="radio"/>				

18. On what level does your library work or liaise with the following bodies in the advancement of OE / OER?

Please choose one response per row.

	Regular	Ad-hoc	None	N/a	Don't know
Academic Departments	<input type="radio"/>				
Assistive Technology or Disability Services	<input type="radio"/>				
Communications Office	<input type="radio"/>				
E-Learning/Distance Education	<input type="radio"/>				
Faculty	<input type="radio"/>				
ICT Staff	<input type="radio"/>				
Legal Department	<input type="radio"/>				
Students, e.g. undergrads and postgrads	<input type="radio"/>				
Senior Administration	<input type="radio"/>				
Student Services	<input type="radio"/>				
Teaching and Learning Centre	<input type="radio"/>				
Vice-rectorate or equivalent	<input type="radio"/>				
Research Centre or Service	<input type="radio"/>				
Regional/National Networks/communities/consortia	<input type="radio"/>				
International Networks/communities/consortia	<input type="radio"/>				
Graduate Schools	<input type="radio"/>				
Other libraries	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please specify)

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY

We would like to understand your institutional policy context in this section. We refer to policy as a written document that stipulates the expectations related to OE for an institution. Its goal is to lead to the creation, increased use and/or support for improving OER. Beyond an institutional policy document, institutional strategic plans, laws, rules, green papers, white papers, roadmaps, declarations, and funding programmes are included in policy.

* 19. Does your organisation have a policy that addresses OE in any way?

- Yes
- Under development
- Under consideration
- No
- I don't know

If yes, please add link here:

DEVELOPING SUPPORTIVE POLICY (continued)

20. Is your organisation's OE policy part of a larger, overarching internal policy, or is it a standalone policy dedicated to OE?

- Part of a larger, overarching policy
- Standalone policy dedicated to Open Education
- Don't know

21. Was your library involved in the policy conception?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

ENCOURAGING EFFECTIVE, INCLUSIVE AND EQUITABLE ACCESS TO QUALITY OER

This section explores to what extent you address accessibility and inclusiveness in your OE work, including online and offline OERs, gender-sensitive, culturally and linguistically relevant OER.

* 22. Does your library take proactive steps to provide/create relevant OER that are designed to be:

Please choose one response per row.

	Yes	No	Don't know
Sensitive (in relation to different ages, races, genders, social-economic statuses, etc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Culturally equitable (embodying the values, policies, and practices of all people)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Linguistically diverse (in local languages and in at least one second language)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Accessible (to meet both needs and material circumstances of target learners e.g. available offline, in printed version, etc)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Other (please specify)

23. We are keen to work to encourage effective, inclusive and equitable access , and would like to showcase good practices.

Are you willing for SPARC Europe to contact you regarding this?

- Yes
 No

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

ENCOURAGING EFFECTIVE, INCLUSIVE AND EQUITABLE ACCESS TO
QUALITY OER (continued)

24. Please provide your contact details

Name

Email Address

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

ENCOURAGING EFFECTIVE, INCLUSIVE AND EQUITABLE ACCESS TO
QUALITY OER (continued)

25. Does your library ensure that promoting effective and inclusive access are reflected in OER strategies and programmes?

Here we are referring to gender equality, diversity, racial justice, equity, accessibility, and inclusiveness.

- Yes
- No
- N/a
- Don't know

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

ENCOURAGING EFFECTIVE, INCLUSIVE AND EQUITABLE ACCESS TO
QUALITY OER (continued)

26. How does your library ensure that gender equality, diversity, racial justice, equity, accessibility, and inclusiveness are reflected in OER strategies and programmes?

- Via a Working Group
- In collaboration with our diversity, equity and inclusion (DEI) Office
- As part of an institutional-wide programme or in accordance with the institutional strategy
- Other (please specify)

- Don't know

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

SUSTAINING OER

27. How many FTE (full time equivalent) staff members are dedicated to working on OE in your library? Note this excludes Open Access, Open Scholarship or Open Science.

- 0
- 1 or less
- 1-5
- 6-9
- 10 or more
- Don't know

* 28. Does your organisation have a grant programme or seed funding for OE work to encourage and assist members in your organisation to create OERs?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

If yes, please provide the name of this programme or project and preferably a link to more information

29. Where does your library get its funding for OE?

Please select all that apply

- Library budget
- Other institutional budget
- A national or regional project or programme
- A European project
- Other (please specify)

- Don't know

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

PROMOTING AND REINFORCING INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

* 30. Is your library involved in creating, maintaining or participating in OE networks or programmes?

	Yes	No	Don't know
Networks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Projects / programmes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If yes, please list them

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES

31. What top three opportunities or benefits have you identified in supporting Open Education in your library?

Your responses may be up to 500 characters per opportunity/benefit.

Opportunity/Benefit 1

Opportunity/Benefit 2

Opportunity/Benefit 3

32. What are your top three key challenges in supporting Open Education in your library?

Your responses may be up to 500 characters per challenge.

Key challenge 1

Key challenge 2

Key challenge 3

33. How did the COVID-19 pandemic affect OE at your institution?

Please choose one response per row.

	Increase	Decrease	No change	Don't know
Use of OER	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Creation of OER	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Awareness of the need for Openness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
OE Policy development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please specify if "Other"

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS

34. If you would like to add any further comments to your survey response, please include these below.

Open Education (OE) in European Libraries of Higher Education Survey 2022

END OF SURVEY

Thank you very much for taking this survey.